

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS OF FAN BLADE FLUTTER UNDER INLET DISTORTION: REVIEWING STATE-OF-THE-ART, DISPELLING MYTHS AND PROPOSING EFFICIENT NUMERICAL METHODS

Dingxi Wang, Yuxuan Zhang

School of Power and Energy
Northwestern Polytechnical University
1 Dongxiang Road, Xi'an, Shaanxi, P.R. China

Xiaohe Yang

Aero-Engine Corporation of China
Commercial Aircraft Corporation Ltd

Dejun Meng

Aero-Engine Corporation of China
Shenyang Aeroengine Research Institute

Peng Zhang

Aero-Engine Corporation of China
Hunan Aviation Powerplant Research Institute

Mu Li

College of Engineering Physics
Shenzhen Technology University
Shenzhen 518118, China

ABSTRACT

Fan blade flutter has been a thoroughly researched field and there are well-established numerical methods for fan blade flutter analysis under clean inlet conditions. However, fan blade flutter under inlet distortion is under-researched. Nevertheless, it has been gaining increasing attention. This is largely attributed to the development of ultra high-bypass-ratio engines and boundary layer ingesting engines. Inlet distortion introduces great complexity to fan blade flutter analysis. To one's surprise, time domain methods have so far been the exclusive methods for fan blade flutter analysis under inlet distortion. What is even more surprising is that there has been a persistent misconception of worksum or work-per-cycle calculation under inlet distortion. In view of this, this paper aims to review the open literature, correct the worksum calculation misconception, and propose more efficient numerical methods for flutter analysis under inlet distortion. To this end, two efficient numerical methods are proposed: the time domain harmonic balance method and the approximate time domain nonlinear harmonic method. To achieve an accurate aerodamping calculation, not only the blade vibration and inlet distortion frequencies but also their scattered frequencies have to be resolved if the time domain harmonic balance method is to be used. However, the approximate time

domain nonlinear harmonic method can achieve comparable accuracy without resolving their scattered frequencies, making the method much more efficient. The efficacy of the two methods is demonstrated through a case study using the NASA rotor 67 with inlet total pressure distortion.

Keywords: flutter, inlet distortion, the time domain harmonic balance method, the approximate time domain nonlinear harmonic method, time-domain method, fluid-structure coupled method, fluid-structure decoupled method, fan blade

NOMENCLATURE

Q conservative variable vector
 V volume of cell
 N Number of harmonics
 τ pseudo time
 f frequency
 β inflow angle
 p unsteady pressure

1 INTRODUCTION

For aircraft engines, inlet distortion is an unavoidable phenomenon. Driven by the key objectives of weight reduction and drag minimization, the nacelle design of modern high-bypass-ratio civil engines has become increasingly compact, with a continuously shortened length. A direct consequence of this design trend is the intensification of flow field distortion at the fan inlet. For boundary layer ingesting (BLI) propulsors, the distortion at the fan inlet is even more severe, subjecting the engine to adverse inlet conditions throughout its operation.

Inlet distortion affects both the aerodynamic and aeroelastic performance of a fan. Extensive research has been conducted on the aerodynamic impact of inlet distortion, leading to a widely accepted understanding that it reduces fan stall margin. However, studies on its influence on fan blade flutter characteristics remain significantly lacking.

The flutter characteristics of fan blades are crucial to the safe operation of an engine. Flutter is a critical issue in fan design that must be avoided at all costs. As fan blade loading increases, structural designs become more compact, and advanced three-dimensional design features and lightweight materials are adopted, the risk of fan blade flutter becomes increasingly prominent.

Inlet distortion disrupts the axisymmetry of an incoming airflow, posing significant challenges to existing efficient flutter analysis methods, as commonly used efficient flutter analysis methods are no longer applicable. The intensity and circumferential scale of distorted flow fields typically induce highly nonlinear unsteady flow characteristics. Thus numerical methods must be capable of capturing these nonlinear effects.

Currently, flutter analyses under inlet distortion invariably rely on time-domain methods, often requiring multi-passage or even full-annulus computational domains. These numerical methods can be further classified into two categories based on the coupling characteristics in solving the flow governing equations and structural dynamics equations: fluid-structure decoupled methods and coupled methods. In the following, the two categories of numerical methods are reviewed with an emphasis on the decoupled methods.

2 A CRITICAL REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

According to the current open literature, the vast majority of numerical analyses of blade flutter under inlet distortion have employed the fluid-structure decoupled methods. These methods first obtain the natural vibration modes and frequencies of a blade through modal analysis. Then, the blade undergoes a small amplitude harmonic vibration according to the prescribed mode and frequency. By solving the flow governing equations, which are often the unsteady Favre-averaged Navier-Stokes (FANS) equations, the unsteady flow induced by the blade vibration is obtained. Finally, the work done by the unsteady flow on the blade

over one vibration cycle, known as the worksum or work-per-cycle, is calculated. If the unsteady flow does work on the blade, meaning the worksum is positive, the blade will experience flutter. Otherwise, the blade will not experience flutter.

Under inlet distortion, particular attention is needed when the worksum is calculated. To be more specific, the unsteady aerodynamic force generated by the inlet distortion needs to be filtered when the worksum is calculated. Otherwise, the consequence is that **the calculated worksum or aerodamping may vary with time [1–5] (e.g. Fig. 1), and the worksum for each blade may also differ [2–4, 6, 7] (e.g. Fig. 2).** In some cases, **the sign of a blade’s worksum may change over time [2, 3, 5], or the sign of worksum varies from one blade to another [2, 3, 6].** This poses difficulties for determining whether a fan or a compressor will experience flutter based on the energy method.

FIGURE 1: Aerodamping variation with time when the aerodynamic forcing due to inlet distortion is not filtered in the worksum calculation [1]

FIGURE 2: Worksum variation with blades when the aerodynamic forcing due to inlet distortion is not filtered in the worksum calculation [4]

This variation of worksum with time and blade can be explained mathematically. We assume that the unsteady flows corresponding to blade vibration and inlet distortion are given by

$$p_1(t, j) = p_{a1} \sin(\omega_1 t + j\delta_1 + \phi_{1p}) \quad (1)$$

$$p_2(t, j) = p_{a2} \sin(\omega_2 t + j\delta_2 + \phi_{2p}) \quad (2)$$

where the subscripts 1 and 2 denote blade vibration and inlet distortion, respectively. It should be noted that unsteady flows due to inlet distortion are nonlinear, and thus there are harmonics in the unsteady flows. Here we look at one frequency component only. p_a denotes the amplitude of an unsteady flow component. ω is the angular frequency. j is the blade index, ranging from 0 to $N_b - 1$ where N_b is the number of blades. δ is the inter blade phase angle. ϕ is a phase angle related to the initial position of a blade, etc. The blade vibration velocity is given by

$$\vec{v}(t, j) = \vec{v}_a \sin(\omega_1 t + j\delta_1 + \phi_v) \quad (3)$$

Now we first derive the work done by the unsteady flow due to blade vibration

$$W_1 = \int_S \int_{t_1}^{t_2} p_1 \vec{n} \cdot \vec{v} dt ds \quad (4)$$

$$= \int_S \int_{t_1}^{t_2} p_{a1} \vec{n} \cdot \vec{v}_a \sin(\omega_1 t + j\delta_1 + \phi_{1p}) \sin(\omega_1 t + j\delta_1 + \phi_v) dt ds \quad (5)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \int_S \int_{t_1}^{t_2} p_{a1} \vec{n} \cdot \vec{v}_a [\cos(\phi_{1p} - \phi_v) - \cos(2\omega_1 t + 2\delta_1 j + \phi_{1p} + \phi_v)] dt ds \quad (6)$$

$$= \frac{(t_2 - t_1)}{2} \int_S p_{a1} \vec{n} \cdot \vec{v}_a \cos(\phi_{1p} - \phi_v) ds \quad (7)$$

$$- \frac{1}{4\omega_1} \int_S p_{a1} \vec{n} \cdot \vec{v}_a [\sin(2\omega_1 t_2 + 2\delta_1 j + \phi_{1p} + \phi_v) - \sin(2\omega_1 t_1 + 2\delta_1 j + \phi_{1p} + \phi_v)] ds \quad (8)$$

What can be seen from the above is that, if $(t_2 - t_1)$ is a multiple of $\frac{2\pi}{\omega_1}$, then we have $2\omega_1 t_2 - 2\omega_1 t_1 = 2\omega_1(t_2 - t_1)$ which is a multiple of 2π . This means Eq. 8 is zero. With this, Eq. 4 is reduced to

$$W_1 = \frac{(t_2 - t_1)}{2} \int_S p_{a1} \vec{n} \cdot \vec{v}_a \cos(\phi_{1p} - \phi_v) ds \quad (9)$$

What we can conclude from this worksum formula is that W_1 is a constant: it does not vary with time (t_1) or blade (j).

Now we derive the work done by the unsteady flow due to inlet distortion

$$W_2 = \int_S \int_{t_1}^{t_2} p_2 \vec{n} \cdot \vec{v} dt ds \quad (10)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \int_S \int_{t_1}^{t_2} p_{a2} \vec{n} \cdot \vec{v}_a \{ \cos[(\omega_2 - \omega_1)t + (\delta_2 - \delta_1)j + \phi_{2p} - \phi_v] - \cos[(\omega_1 + \omega_2)t + (\delta_1 + \delta_2)j + \phi_{2p} + \phi_v] \} dt ds \quad (11)$$

If $\omega_1 = \omega_2$, then we have

$$W_2 = \frac{t_2 - t_1}{2} \int_S p_{a2} \vec{n} \cdot \vec{v}_a \cos[(\delta_2 - \delta_1)j + \phi_{2p} - \phi_v] ds \quad (12)$$

$$- \frac{1}{4\omega_1} \int_S p_{a2} \vec{n} \cdot \vec{v}_a \{ \sin[2\omega_1 t_2 + (\delta_1 + \delta_2)j + \phi_{2p} + \phi_v] - \sin[2\omega_1 t_1 + (\delta_1 + \delta_2)j + \phi_{2p} + \phi_v] \} ds \quad (13)$$

If $(t_2 - t_1)$ is a multiple of $\frac{2\pi}{\omega_1}$, then Eq. 13 is zero. With this, the worksum of W_2 is reduced to

$$W_2 = \frac{t_2 - t_1}{2} \int_S p_{a2} \vec{n} \cdot \vec{v}_a \cos[(\delta_2 - \delta_1)j + \phi_{2p} - \phi_v] ds \quad (14)$$

There is some difference between the worksum in Eq. 9 and that in Eq. 14. Equation 9 does not depend on the inter blade phase angle. If $\delta_2 - \delta_1 \neq 0$, then the worksum differs from blade to blade. If $\delta_2 = \delta_1$, then the worksum is reduced to

$$W_2 = \frac{t_2 - t_1}{2} \int_S p_{a2} \vec{n} \cdot \vec{v}_a \cos(\phi_{2p} - \phi_v) ds \quad (15)$$

The above equation has the same form as Eq. 9. Its value is the same for all blades.

In general, $\omega_1 \neq \omega_2$, then we have

$$W_2 = \frac{1}{2(\omega_2 - \omega_1)} \int_S p_{a2} \vec{n} \cdot \vec{v}_a \{ \sin[(\omega_2 - \omega_1)t_2 + (\delta_2 - \delta_1)j + \phi_{2p} - \phi_v] - \sin[(\omega_2 - \omega_1)t_1 + (\delta_2 - \delta_1)j + \phi_{2p} - \phi_v] \} ds \quad (16)$$

$$- \frac{1}{2(\omega_2 + \omega_1)} \int_S p_{a2} \vec{n} \cdot \vec{v}_a \{ \sin[(\omega_1 + \omega_2)t_2 + (\delta_1 + \delta_2)j + \phi_{2p} + \phi_v] - \sin[(\omega_1 + \omega_2)t_1 + (\delta_1 + \delta_2)j + \phi_{2p} + \phi_v] \} ds \quad (17)$$

If $(t_2 - t_1)$ is a multiple of both $\frac{2\pi}{\omega_2 - \omega_1}$ and $\frac{2\pi}{\omega_1 + \omega_2}$, then Eq. 16 is equal to zero. This is determined by the orthogonality of trigonometric functions. If $(t_2 - t_1)$ is not a multiple of $\frac{2\pi}{\omega_2 - \omega_1}$ or $\frac{2\pi}{\omega_1 + \omega_2}$, then Eq. 16 will generally not be zero and vary with time (t_1).

Now we use the conclusions from the above section to analyze Fig.17 in reference [6]. To facilitate our analysis, we include it in Fig. 3. What we can see from Fig. 3 is that the patterns of the aerodamping varies with the nodal diameter. The number of patterns for nodal diameters 1, -2, -8 and 8 are 3, 0, 6 and 10, respectively. In this work, the blade vibration frequency is twice the blade shaft frequency which is also the fundamental frequency of the inlet distortion unsteady flow. Due to the nonlinearity, the unsteady flow due to inlet distortion has the frequencies of $0.5n\omega_1$, where n is an integer. In the worksum calculation, the time integration interval is twice the blade vibration period, which is the common period of all unsteady flow components. This means the work done by an unsteady flow component with a frequency that is not ω_1 will be filtered in the time integration. However, for the inlet distortion induced unsteady flow component with the frequency of ω_1 , its work done on the blade cannot be filtered through the time integration. This inlet distortion unsteady flow component has a nodal diameter of -2. By referring to Eq. 14, we can conclude that its work done on a vibrating blade varies with

FIGURE 3: Variation of aerodynamic damping with blade index for four different nodal diameters: (a) 1ND TW, (b) 2ND BTW, (c) 8ND BTW, and (d) 8ND FTW. [6]

blade if the blade vibration nodal diameter is not -2. The number of patterns of the calculated worksum variation is decided by the inter blade phase angle difference $\delta_2 - \delta_1$ in Eq. 14. It is not difficult to derive that the number of worksum variation patterns is the difference between the inlet distortion nodal diameter and a blade vibration nodal diameter: $|-2 - N|$. N is the blade vibration nodal diameter. Referring to Fig. 3, for vibration nodal diameters of 1, -2, -8 and 8, the number of patterns can be calculated to be 3, 0, 6 and 10. This is consistent with the number of patterns shown in the figure.

One of the methods to filter out the unsteady aerodynamic work caused by inlet distortion is to set the time integration interval of the worksum to a common multiple of the distortion and vibration periods. Yan et al. [6], Corral et al. [5], and Chen et al. [2] have respectively studied cases where the blade vibration frequency is 2 times, 1.5 times, and 3 times the fundamental frequency of the inlet distortion unsteady flow, setting the time interval for calculating the worksum to 2 times, 2 times, and 3 times the blade vibration period. This approach is effective when the least common multiple of the distortion's fundamental frequency and the blade vibration frequency is small. However, when the least common multiple of the blade vibration frequency and the distortion's fundamental frequency is large, this method requires advancing the unsteady calculation over a very long time period, making it extremely time-consuming.

Iseni et al. [1] used the blade vibration period as the integration interval in their worksum calculations, advancing the computation for about 25 blade vibration periods. They monitored the variation of worksum with time iterations and finally performed a time averaging on the worksum time series to facilitate the measurement of blade flutter characteristics. Chen et

al. [2] found that the blade's worksum essentially stabilized and no longer varied with time after extending the integration time interval of worksum to 12 times the blade vibration period.

Another method to filter the unsteady aerodynamic work caused by inlet distortion is the approach proposed by Chennuru et al. [8]. This method employs a Fourier series to fit the modal aerodynamic force, thereby extracting the modal aerodynamic force corresponding to the unsteady flow of blade vibration for calculating the worksum or aerodynamic damping. In their curve fitting, they accounted for the blade vibration frequency, the distortion frequency and its harmonics, and the scattering frequencies resulting from the interaction between blade vibration and distortion, totaling 25 frequencies. Since this modal aerodynamic force extraction is a post-process that does not involve solving large systems of equations, the computational time is negligible.

If the distortion flow field contains flow components with a frequency matching the blade vibration frequency, setting the time integration interval of the worksum to the common period of distortion and vibration fails to filter out the unsteady aerodynamic work of the distortion flow at that frequency. In the study by Yan et al. [6], the blade vibration frequency was exactly 2 times the shaft frequency. Although they used a time interval of 2 times the blade vibration period for calculating the worksum, and the resulting worksum did not vary with time, the worksum differed among blades in the circumferential direction. Chen et al. [2] investigated a case where the blade vibration frequency was 3 times the shaft frequency and observed a phenomenon consistent with that encountered by Yan et al. [6]: the worksum varied across different blades. To address this issue, Chen et al. [2] averaged the worksum across different blades. This spatial averaging effectively filters the unsteady aerodynamic work caused by distortion in the spatial domain. However, it should be noted that when the nodal diameter of the unsteady distortion flow matches that of the blade vibration, the worksum becomes identical across all blades. In such cases, spatial averaging cannot filter out the unsteady aerodynamic work induced by inlet distortion. Calculations by Chen et al. [2] revealed an anomaly in the aerodynamic damping-nodal diameter curve at the nodal diameter of -3, where the aerodynamic damping was excessively small (as shown in Figure 4). This occurs because the worksum calculation fails to filter out the distortion aerodynamic work, which acted as an excitation source, resulting in a significantly underestimated aerodynamic damping.

In fluid-structure decoupled numerical analysis, the vast majority of decoupled methods employ full-annulus computational domains, resulting in significant computational effort and time consumption. To reduce computational time, Corral et al. [5] proposed a method to simultaneously compute aerodynamic damping for multiple nodal diameters. The number of nodal diameters and the vibration amplitude corresponding to each nodal diameter are tied to ensuring mesh quality during a computation.

FIGURE 4: Aerodynamic damping characteristics of the TUDa compressor rotor under distorted and uniform inlet conditions (When ND=-3, the aerodynamic damping under distorted conditions includes excitation from the distorted flow field) [2]

This method assumes that the unsteady flow components generated by vibrations at different nodal diameters have small amplitudes and do not interact nonlinearly. When using this method to calculate worksum, in addition to time filtering, spatial filtering is also required to separate the worksum work associated with different nodal diameters.

Another approach to reduce computational effort is the multi-frequency shape correction method proposed by He [9]. This method uses a truncated Fourier series to approximate the flow field at geometric periodic boundaries and dynamically updates the coefficients of the truncated Fourier series. It can be applied to flutter analysis under inlet distortion conditions, significantly reducing computer memory consumption. Li et al. [10] utilized this method to analyze the flutter characteristics of fan blades under inlet distortion conditions. Compared to multi-passage or full-annulus computations, this method can improve computational efficiency by 5-10 times, with specific results depending on the blade vibration nodal diameter and distortion nodal diameter. Iseni et al. [1] applied this method to flutter analysis under inlet distortion conditions, and the computational results showed good agreement with those obtained from half-annulus computational domains.

Yan et al. [6] proposed a fast method for distortion flutter analysis. This approach combines flutter analysis results under uniform inlet conditions with the aerodynamic work done by the unsteady distortion flow when the blade is not vibrating, superimposing the distortion aerodynamic work onto the blade vibration worksum under uniform inlet conditions. The flutter analysis under uniform inlet conditions can leverage commonly used efficient numerical methods, while the computation of the distortion flow field does not need to account for blade vibra-

tion and requires only a single calculation. Numerical studies indicate that the results of this method align in trend with computations that simultaneously consider distortion and blade vibration, though some quantitative differences exist. It should be noted that this method does not account for the mutual coupling between the distortion flow field and blade vibration. If the time-averaged flow field under distortion conditions differs significantly from the steady flow field under uniform inlet conditions, the computational error introduced by this method may be substantial. Additionally, the worksum used to assess blade flutter characteristics must filter out the unsteady aerodynamic work of the distortion flow, casting doubt on the validity of this fast method.

Only a few studies in the open literature employ fluid-structure coupled methods to analyze flutter under distortion conditions. These fluid-structure coupled methods all involve solving reduced-order structural dynamics equations. Specifically, modal analysis is first conducted to obtain the natural vibration modes and frequencies of a blade, followed by the construction of a reduced-order structural dynamics equation. The flow governing equations and the reduced-order structural dynamics equations are then solved in a coupled manner. Moreover, in the open literature, fluid-structure coupled flutter analyses under inlet distortion conditions typically assume that blade vibration is nodal diameter vibration, implying that inlet distortion does not cause blade vibration mistuning. Nevertheless, fluid-structure coupled numerical analyses by Henrick et al. [3] demonstrated that the vibration amplitudes of different blades were not identical.

Under inlet distortion conditions, if the frequency of the distortion flow field is close to the blade's natural frequency, or if the distortion intensity is sufficiently large, the blade will undergo corresponding vibrations due to the excitation from the unsteady distortion flow, known as forced vibration. During flutter analysis, the blade vibration displacement comprises both forced vibration (the particular solution of the equation) and flutter (the general solution of the equation). The coupling of these two vibrations poses challenges in extracting aerodynamic damping from the blade vibration modal displacement. Typically, the forced vibration component in the blade vibration displacement must be filtered out [5]. Zheng et al. [11, 12] employed a notch filter to remove the forced vibration displacement and subsequently calculated the aerodynamic damping based on the time evolution of the filtered blade vibration amplitude.

In summary, the majority of numerical methods for flutter analysis under inlet distortion conditions are based on multi-passage or even full-annulus computational domains, employing time-domain time-marching methods. These methods require substantial computational resources and are difficult to apply in routine engineering design. To improve the efficiency of numerical analysis, Iseni et al. [1] and Li et al. [10] utilized a single-passage computational domain with a multi-frequency

shape-correction method, achieving 5–10 times acceleration in computation. Corral et al. [5] proposed a decoupled fluid-structure interaction method for full-annulus domains considering multiple nodal diameters, which also achieved certain acceleration. Nevertheless, compared to frequency-domain methods commonly used for flutter analysis under uniform inlet conditions (such as the linear harmonic method [13] and the nonlinear harmonic method [14]) or hybrid time-frequency methods (e.g., time-domain harmonic balance [15] and nonlinear frequency-domain method [16]), the computational time of these methods generally increases by at least an order of magnitude. Moreover, when the frequency and nodal diameter of the distorted unsteady flow match those of the blade vibration (where resonance occurs), none of the existing methods can accurately compute the aerodynamic damping. In light of this, it is essential to develop more efficient and general numerical methods for flutter analysis under inlet distortion that are suitable for routine engineering applications.

3 CASE STUDY

In this study, the NASA rotor 67 was used to investigate flutter analysis under inlet distortion. First, a series of steady analyses were performed to establish the speedline of the rotor at its design speed under clean inlet flow. The purpose is twofold. One is to validate the flow solver for aerodynamic analysis. The other is to provide a baseline for analysis under inlet distortion. Second, the unsteady flow due to inlet distortion was analyzed using both a time domain time marching method and the time domain harmonic balance method. The purpose here is twofold. One is to verify the time domain harmonic balance method for analyzing inlet distortion unsteady flow. The other is to establish the number of harmonics needed for an accurate analysis of inlet distortion unsteady flow using the time domain harmonic balance method. Third, a series of flutter analyses were performed for the NASA rotor 67 under inlet distortion using the time domain harmonic balance method. This is to establish the frequency set needed for an accurate flutter analysis under inlet distortion. Fourth, the more efficient numerical method - the approximate time domain nonlinear harmonic method was proposed for flutter analysis under inlet distortion. The accuracy of the method was verified using the time domain harmonic balance method. Its efficiency was also demonstrated through comparison with the time domain harmonic balance method. Finally, a fluid-structure coupled analysis was performed for the NASA rotor 67 under inlet distortion. The purpose is to obtain the reference results to verify the efficient numerical methods: the time domain harmonic balance method and the approximate time domain nonlinear harmonic method.

3.1 STEADY ANALYSIS

A multi-block structured grid was generated for the rotor. The total number of grid points per passage is about 0.66 million. The blade-to-blade view and meridional view of the grid are shown in Fig.5.

FIGURE 5: The grid of the NASA Rotor 67

All the steady analyses were performed using the in-house flow solver - TurboXDM [17–19] on a computational domain consisting of one blade passage. At the domain inlet, total pressure and total temperature corresponding to the ISO condition, together with axial flow direction were imposed. At the domain outlet, area-averaged static pressure was prescribed. The static pressure was varied to obtain a speedline of the rotor at the design speed. On a solid wall, a slip wall condition together with a wall function was used to reduce near wall mesh density. At the rotational periodic boundaries at the lateral direction, the rotational periodic boundary condition was applied.

Figure 6 presents both the calculated speedline and the experimental data. The numerical results are in good agreement with the test data, though pressure ratio, efficiency and stall margin are slightly under-predicted. The under-prediction is not uncommon with a steady Favre-averaged Navier-Stokes analysis [6, 11].

3.2 INLET DISTORTION UNSTEADY FLOW ANALYSIS

This subsection presents an analysis of unsteady flow due to inlet distortion. The distorted total pressure distribution is shown in Fig. 7. It was generated using a distortion screen during a rig test. The total pressure was measured using 8 radial rakes, which were uniformly distributed in the circumferential direction. Each rake has 6 total pressure probes. The total pressure deficit is confined to a small region spanning about 80°. This total pressure was mapped to the inlet of the NASA rotor 67.

A fourth-order Fourier series can be used to fit the total pressure distribution in the circumferential direction. Figure 8 shows the comparison of the Fourier-series fitted total pressure distribution and the discrete measurement data at three typical span locations. The curves go through all the data points as expected.

FIGURE 6: Speedlines of the NASA Rotor 67 at its design speed

FIGURE 7: Total pressure distribution with distortion

FIGURE 8: Fourier series representation of the total pressure circumferential distribution at three typical span locations

To analyze the unsteady flow due to inlet distortion using a time domain time marching method, a whole annulus computational domain was used. Four different time steps, namely, $T/100$, $T/200$, $T/400$ and $T/1100$, were used to perform time step independence study. T is the fundamental period of the unsteady flow. It is the same as the reciprocal of the blade shaft frequency. Figure 9 presents the amplitudes and phase angles of the first harmonic of the unsteady pressure. To accurately resolve the first harmonic of the unsteady pressure, the time step has to be $T/400$.

FIGURE 9: Amplitude and phase distribution of the first harmonic unsteady pressure along the axial chord at 90% span, computed using the dual time-stepping method with different time steps.

Figure 10 shows the time histories of unsteady pressure around the leading edge of four blades at 90% span. It can be seen that the static pressure settles into a time-periodic state after about two periods. A spectral analysis of the static pressure time history is presented in Fig. 10b. It can be seen that the first three harmonics are the major components. It implies that at least three harmonics are needed to represent the static pressure with acceptable accuracy.

Figure 11 shows the instantaneous entropy distribution at 90% span. The high entropy flow in the distorted region of the inlet is convected downstream. When it is convected through the blade passages, it is also pushed in the direction of the blade rotation. The flow non-uniformity is not fully mixed out even at the outlet of the computational domain.

Following the time domain time marching analysis of the unsteady flow, the time domain harmonic balance method was also used to analyze the unsteady flow. Different from the time domain time marching analysis, a single passage computational domain was used. Four different sets of analyses with 3, 5, 7 and 9 harmonics were performed to establish the minimum number of harmonics required for an accurate analysis. Figure 12

(a) History of the unsteady pressure under inlet distortion

(b) FFT analysis

FIGURE 10: History of the unsteady pressure under inlet distortion and FFT analysis

FIGURE 11: Instantaneous entropy at 90% span

presents the amplitude and phase of the first harmonic unsteady pressure at 90% span. At least five harmonics are needed to achieve an accuracy comparable with that of the reference time domain analysis results.

(a) harmonic amplitude

(b) harmonic phase

FIGURE 12: Amplitude and phase distribution of the first harmonic unsteady pressure along the axial chord at 90% span, computed using the time-domain harmonic balance method with different numbers of harmonics.

3.3 FLUTTER ANALYSIS UNDER INLET DISTORTION USING THE TIME DOMAIN HARMONIC BALANCE METHOD

The first bending mode was considered in the flutter analysis under inlet distortion. Figure 13 shows the mode shape of the first bending mode. The frequency of this mode is 537.93Hz, which is close to the second engine order(534.77Hz). The results were obtained in a blade-alone modal analysis, which ignores structural coupling between blades and the disk.

FIGURE 13: Modal displacement of the first bending mode

A few attempts were made to perform flutter analysis under inlet distortion using the time domain harmonic balance method. In all these analyses, a single-passage computational domain was used, unless stated otherwise. In the first attempt, six harmonics were retained in the analysis. Five harmonics were for the inlet distortion unsteady flow and one harmonic was for the blade vibration unsteady flow.

It was discovered that the calculated logarithmic decrement(log-dec) varied with the circumferential position of the inlet distortion, as shown in Fig. 14. The analyses were performed for the same zero nodal diameter. Four different inlet distortion positions were considered. Among the four calculations, the biggest log-dec is about eight times the smallest log-dec. On one side, such a big variation of log-dec cannot be considered the culprit of rounding errors. On the other side, such a variation is counterintuitive.

To understand how the calculated log-dec varies with the circumferential position of inlet distortion, the amplitudes of the blade vibration unsteady pressure at 90% span are shown in Fig. 15. The blade vibration unsteady pressure also varies with the circumferential position of the inlet distortion.

This variation of unsteady pressure implies that the unsteady pressure will also vary from passage to passage if a whole annulus domain is used. To verify this speculation, a time domain harmonic balance analysis was performed on a whole annulus domain for the zero nodal diameter vibration. Figure 16 shows the unsteady pressure amplitude due to blade vibration at 90% span. As expected, the pressure amplitude varies considerably

FIGURE 14: Logarithmic decrement from flutter analysis under inlet distortion at different circumferential positions obtained using the time domain harmonic balance method with the settings of 5 harmonics for inlet distortion, 1 harmonic for blade vibration for the first bending mode with zero nodal diameter

FIGURE 15: Unsteady pressure amplitude distribution at 90% blade height, caused by the blade vibration under inlet distortion at different circumferential positions, the TDHB method: $N=6$ (5 harmonics for inlet distortion, 1 harmonic for blade vibration), first bending mode, $ND=0$

from one passage to another.

It was speculated that the solution is nonphysical due to the aliasing effect when scattered frequencies are not resolved. To verify this speculation, the second attempt was to include some scattered frequencies in a time domain harmonic balance analysis for the zero nodal diameter vibration. Four scattered frequencies were included: $n f_2 \pm f_1$, with $n = 1, 2$. f_1 and f_2 denote the blade vibration frequency and the fundamental frequency of the inlet distortion unsteady flow. Figure 17 shows the log-dec for four different circumferential positions of the inlet distortion. The

FIGURE 16: Unsteady pressure amplitude at 90% blade height induced by the blade vibration obtained using the TDHB method without scattered modes on a full-annulus computational domain for the first bending mode with zero nodal diameter.

difference in log-dec between the four calculations is negligible. This verifies our speculation of nonphysical solutions. It also implies that there is a need to include the scattered frequencies in a flutter analysis under inlet distortion.

FIGURE 17: Logarithmic decrement from flutter analysis under inlet distortion at different circumferential positions obtained using the time domain harmonic balance method with the settings of 5 harmonics for inlet distortion, 1 harmonic for blade vibration for the first bending mode with zero nodal diameter ($N=6$: no scattered modes, $N=10$: 4 scattered modes)

For further verification, a time domain harmonic balance analysis was performed on a whole annulus domain for the zero nodal diameter vibration. Figure 18 shows the pressure amplitude of blade vibration unsteady flow at 90% span. Consistent with the log-dec calculation, the difference in unsteady pressure amplitude from different passages is negligible.

FIGURE 18: Unsteady pressure amplitude at 90% blade height induced by the blade vibration obtained using the TDHB method with four scattered modes on a full-annulus computational domain for the first bending mode with zero nodal diameter.

3.4 FLUTTER ANALYSIS UNDER INLET DISTORTION USING THE APPROXIMATE TIME DOMAIN NON-LINEAR HARMONIC METHOD

What we can conclude from the previous section is that scattered frequencies have to be included in a flutter analysis under inlet distortion if the time domain harmonic balance method is to be used. The major drawback of including these scattered frequencies lies in the associated overhead. It is natural to ask whether we can find a way to eliminate the nonphysical solution without incurring significant overhead.

Before embarking on finding such an efficient method, let us discuss how blade vibration unsteady flow is generated. When a blade vibrates in an unsteady flow, the blade interacts with both the time-averaged part and the time-varying part of the unsteady flow. The interaction with the time-averaged part generates the unsteady flow component with the blade vibration frequency. The interaction with the time-varying part generates those scattered modes whose frequencies are different from the blade vibration frequency.

In a flutter analysis using a decoupled approach, the unsteady flow with the blade vibration frequency is what is needed. Those scattered modes do not contribute to the worksum or aero-damping calculation, due to the orthogonality of trigonometric functions. To avoid resolving the scattered modes, one needs to solve for the blade vibration unsteady flow based upon the time-averaged flow. One natural thinking would be to solve for the inlet distortion unsteady flow first to obtain the time-averaged flow field. Then solve for the blade vibration unsteady flow based upon the time-averaged flow field. This approach is difficult to implement, though it is theoretically feasible.

An ideal approach would be the one that requires little change to an existing time domain harmonic balance solver. To be more specific, we can solve two sets of unsteady flow governing equations: one is for the inlet distortion unsteady flow and the other is for the blade vibration unsteady flow. The two sets of equations are coupled through the time-averaged flow. This is exactly what the approximate time domain nonlinear harmonic method was designed for. Algorithms of the approximate time domain nonlinear harmonic method can be found from reference [20].

An analysis was performed on a whole annulus computa-

tional domain for the zero nodal diameter vibration using the approximate time domain harmonic balance method. Figure 19 shows the amplitude of the unsteady pressure with the blade vibration frequency at 90% span. Compared with Fig. 16, the difference between passages is negligible. This demonstrates the potential of the approximate time domain nonlinear harmonic method for efficient flutter analysis under inlet distortion.

FIGURE 19: Unsteady pressure amplitude at 90% blade height induced by the blade vibration obtained using the ATDNH method on a full-annulus computational domain for the first bending mode with zero nodal diameter.

To verify the approximate time domain nonlinear harmonic method in a quantitative way, an analysis was performed for the zero nodal diameter vibration on a single-passage domain. Figure 20 shows the convergence history of the worksum, together with another three analyses using the time domain harmonic balance method. The approximate time domain nonlinear harmonic method has the fastest convergence. For this particular nodal diameter, the approximate time domain nonlinear harmonic method achieves an accuracy comparable with that of the time domain harmonic balance method with 10 scattered modes. However, the time cost of the approximate time domain nonlinear harmonic method is less than one third of that of the time domain harmonic balance method with 10 scattered modes.

Figure 21 shows area-averaged blade vibration unsteady pressure amplitudes at 90% span. In the figure, ATDNH represents the approximate time domain nonlinear harmonic method, and TDHB represents the time domain harmonic balance method. The ATDNH(N=6) resolves six frequency components. The TDHB(N=6), TDHB(N=10) and TDHB(N=16) resolve six, ten and sixteen frequency components, respectively. With the TDHB(N=6) setting, the amplitudes of f_1 and nf_2 ($n \in [2, 5)$) are all over-predicted when no scattered modes are resolved. When four scattered modes are resolved, the results of the TDHB(N=10) setting are greatly improved. The results can be further improved if more scattered modes are included. Different from the TDHB method, the results of the ATDNH method agree well with those of the TDHB method with 16 harmonics, even no scattered modes are solved.

Figure 22 presents the distribution of the unsteady pressure amplitudes of blade vibration at 90% span and 10% span. The results of the TDHB method without scattered modes are totally wrong. With four scattered modes being resolved, the ac-

FIGURE 20: Convergence histories of worksum under inlet distortion computed using different numerical methods for the first bending mode with zero nodal diameter

FIGURE 21: Unsteady pressure amplitudes of all harmonics at 90%, obtained using different numerical methods and a single-passage computational domain for the first bending mode with zero nodal diameter

curacy is significantly improved. Nevertheless, the results of the TDHB(N=10) are slightly different from the those of the TDHB(N=16). While the results of the ATDNH method agree well with those of the TDHB(N=16).

3.5 VERIFICATION USING TIME DOMAIN COUPLED SOLUTION

To verify the TDHB method and the ATDNH method for flutter analysis under inlet distortion, a series of time-domain fluid-structure coupled analyses were performed to assess aeroelastic stability of the NASA rotor 67. Aerodynamic damping was extracted from blade modal displacements and is used to verify the results of the TDHB method and the ATDNH method. For a time domain fluid-structure coupled analysis, a full-annulus computational domain was adopted. All the blades were prescribed to vibrate in a travelling wave mode. The physical time

FIGURE 22: Unsteady pressure amplitude distributions of the first harmonic induced by blade vibration along the axial chord, obtained using different numerical methods and a single-passage computational domain for the first bending mode with zero nodal diameter

step was set as $\Delta t = T/400$, consistent with that of the inlet distortion time domain analysis. The unsteady FANS equations were solved using the dual-time stepping method with 10 inner iterations. The reduced-order structural dynamics equation was also solved using the dual-time stepping method. The two sets of equations were coupled at each inner time step, leading to a tight and concurrent coupling.

Figure 23 shows the time histories of blade vibration modal displacement under the inlet distortion for the first bending mode with two nodal diameters. For $ND = -1$, the displacement amplitude gradually decreases over time. However, the displacement amplitude does not decrease monotonically, but fluctuates. The increases in blade displacement amplitudes are caused by the forced response to the one engine order (EO) component of the inlet distortion. Since the 1EO's excitation frequency of 267.38Hz differs significantly from the blade's natural frequency of 537.93Hz , the amplitude of this forced response remains relatively small. For $ND = -2$, the displacement amplitude increases over time and eventually stabilizes into a constant amplitude vibration. However, it does not indicate that the blade is undergoing flutter. This occurs because the 2EO's excitation frequency of 534.77Hz is very close to the blade's natural frequency of 537.93Hz , resulting in a near resonance response with a considerable vibration amplitude.

For a clean inlet situation, the log-dec can be calculated by taking the natural logarithm of the ratio of a displacement amplitude to its next one. However, with forced vibration due to inlet distortion, the log-dec cannot be calculated in this way anymore. Therefore, a new method is needed to exclude the influence of forced responses from the inlet distortion for calculating the log-dec.

It can be assumed that the blade vibration displacement con-

FIGURE 23: History of the blade vibration modal displacement under distorted inlet for the first bending mode with two different nodal diameters

sists of two components: one is the forced response displacement induced by the inlet distortion, and the other is the self-excited vibration displacement. Therefore, the total displacement of the blade can be expressed as

$$x(t) = \sum_{n=1}^N A_n \cos(2n\pi f_2 t + \phi_n) + A_0 e^{-\beta t} \cos(2\pi f_1 t + \phi_0) \quad (18)$$

in which A_n and ϕ_n are the n -th amplitude and phase angle of the forced response vibration displacement. A_0 and ϕ_0 are the initial amplitude and phase angle of the self-excited vibration displacement. β is the exponential decay rate associated with the damping of the self-excited vibration. These parameters are determined by using a nonlinear least-squares fitting approach for the time history of blade displacement. The original displacement and fitted displacement are shown in Fig.23, which are in agreement with each other. The corresponding log-dec can be calculated as $\log\text{-dec} = \frac{-\beta}{f_1}$.

Figure 24 compares the variation of log-dec with nodal diameter under both clean and distorted inlet conditions obtained using two fluid-structure interaction decoupled approaches (the TDHB method and the ATDNH method) and one fluid-structure coupled interaction approach (the TD method). Under the clean inlet condition, the variation of log-dec with nodal diameter obtained by the TDHB method agrees closely with that from the TD method. Under distorted inlet conditions, the log-dec trends obtained by the TDHB method and the ATDNH method are also in strong agreement with the results from the TD method. By comparing the results under clean and distorted inlet conditions, it is observed that the lowest log-dec value is reduced by about

15% relative to the clean inlet case, indicating a significant reduction in the aeroelastic stability of the NASA Rotor 67 blade due to inlet distortion.

FIGURE 24: Comparison of the variation of log-dec with nodal diameter under clean inlet and distorted inlet obtained by using the fluid-structure interaction decoupled and coupled approaches

4 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

This paper presents a review of state-of-the-art numerical methods for fan flutter analysis under inlet distortion, explains the unusual work-per-cycle results reported in the open literature, and proposes more efficient numerical methods. It is found that in flutter analysis under inlet distortion, the time-domain harmonic balance method must account for not only the blade vibration and inlet distortion frequencies but also their scattered frequencies. Otherwise, a nonphysical solution will be obtained, leading to the counterintuitive results of worksum variation with blade passage and/or time. The approximate time-domain nonlinear harmonic method does not require the inclusion of these scattered frequencies, as it solves different fundamental frequencies separately and only couples them through time-averaged terms. This significantly reduces computational cost while maintaining acceptable accuracy when performing flutter analysis under inlet distortion. For time-domain flutter analysis, it is necessary to remove the forced response induced by the inlet distortion from the vibration displacement in order to obtain the aerodynamic damping. The time-domain harmonic balance, the approximate time-domain nonlinear harmonic method, and the time-domain method all indicate that the inlet distortion being considered in this study leads to a reduction in aerodynamic damping at its design operating point for the rotor 67.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by the Aviation Science Foundation of China(Grant No. 2023L039053002 and Grant No. 2024M039053001) and the Stable Support for Research Institutes (Project No. 0200850007).

REFERENCES

- [1] Iseni, S., Micallef, D., and Mailach, R., 2016. “Investigation of inlet distortion on the flutter stability of a highly loaded transonic fan rotor”. In Proceedings of ASME Turbo Expo 2016: Turbomachinery Technical Conference and Exposition, GT2016, June 13 – 17, 2016, Seoul, South Korea.
- [2] Chen, H., Xia, K., Deng, H., Zhu, M., and Teng, J., 2025. “Investigation of aeroelastic instability in a transonic compressor with low engine order distortion”. *Aerospace Science and Technology*, **159**, April, p. 109953.
- [3] Herrick, G. P., 2014. “Assessing fan flutter stability in presence of inlet distortion using one-way and two-way coupled methods”. In AIAA 2014-3733, 50th AIAA/ASME/SAE/ASEE Joint Propulsion Conference, July 28-30, 2014, Cleveland, OH.
- [4] Herrick, G. P., 2010. “Effects of inlet distortion on aeromechanical stability of a forward-swept high-speed fan”. In AIAA-2010-6711, 46th AIAA/ASME/SAE/ASEE Joint Propulsion Conference & Exhibit 25 July 2010 - 28 July 2010 Nashville, TN.
- [5] Corral, R., RodriguezBlanco, S., Chennuru, V. Y., Vahdati, M., and Zhao, F., 2024. “A new non-linear time-domain flutter analysis approach for distorted flows”. In GT2024-129404, Proceedings of ASME Turbo Expo 2024 Turbomachinery Technical Conference and Exposition GT2024 June 24-28, 2024, London, United Kingdom.
- [6] Yan, Z., Pan, T., Su, G., Li, Q., and Kielb, R. E., 2024. “Numerical investigation of classic flutter mechanism under circumferentially non-uniform inlet condition”. *Journal of Turbomachinery*, **146**(6), June, p. 061011.
- [7] Bakhle, M. A., Reddy, T., Herrick, G. P., Shabbir, A., and Florea, R. V., 2012. “Aeromechanics analysis of a boundary layer ingesting fan”. In AIAA-2012-3995, 48th AIAA/ASME/SAE/ASEE Joint Propulsion Conference & Exhibit, Atlanta, Georgia.
- [8] Chennuru, V. Y., Rodriguez-Blanco, S., Zhao, F., Corral, R., and Vahdati, M., 2024. “Effects of ground vortex on flutter stability of a fan blade under quiescent conditions”. In GPPS-TC-2024-103, Proceedings of Global Power and Propulsion Society, GPPS Chania24, September 4-6, 2024.
- [9] He, L., 1992. “Method of simulating unsteady turbomachinery flows with multiple perturbations”. *AIAA Journal*, **30**(11), November, pp. 2730–2735.
- [10] Li, H., and He, L., 2002. “Single-passage analysis of unsteady flows around vibrating blades of a transonic fan under inlet distortion”. *Journal of Turbomachinery*, **124**(2), April, pp. 285–292.
- [11] Zheng, Y., Xu, K., Yang, H., Gao, Q., and Jin, X., 2020. “Effects of s-shaped intake on aeromechanical characteristics of a transonic fan”. In Proceedings of ASME Turbo Expo 2020 Turbomachinery Technical Conference and Exposition GT2020 September 21-25, 2020, Virtual, Online.
- [12] Zheng, Y., Guo, P., Yang, H., and Xu, K., 2023. “Effects of inlet distortion on aeroelastic stability of a transonic fan”. In GPPS-TC-2023-0090, Proceedings of Global Power and Propulsion Society, GPPS Hong Kong 2023, October 17-19, 2023.
- [13] Hall, K., and Lorence, C., 1993. “Calculation of three-dimensional unsteady flows in turbomachinery using the linearized harmonic Euler equations”. *Journal of Turbomachinery*, **115**(4), pp. 800–809.
- [14] He, L., and Ning, W., 1998. “An efficient approach for analysis of unsteady viscous flows in turbomachines”. *AIAA Journal*, **36**(11), pp. 2005–2012.
- [15] Hall, K., Thomas, J., and Clark, W., 2002. “Computation of unsteady nonlinear flows in cascades using a harmonic balance technique”. *AIAA Journal*, **40**(5), pp. 879–886.
- [16] McMullen, M., Jameson, A., and Alonso, J., 2006. “Demonstration of nonlinear frequency domain methods”. *AIAA Journal*, **44**(44), pp. 1428–1435.
- [17] Wang, D., and Huang, X., 2017. “A complete rotor-stator coupling method for frequency domain analysis of turbomachinery unsteady flow”. *Aerospace Science and Technology*, **70**, pp. 367–377.
- [18] Wang, D., and Huang, X., 2017. “Solution stabilization and convergence acceleration for the harmonic balance equation system”. *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, **139**(9), p. 092503.
- [19] Wang, D., Zhang, S., Huang, X., and Huang, H., 2022. “Coupled time and passage spectral method for an efficient resolution of turbomachinery far upstream wakes”. *Journal of Turbomachinery*, **144**(2), p. 021006.
- [20] Wang, D., Zhang, S., and Huang, X., 2021. “An approximate time domain nonlinear harmonic method for analyzing unsteady flows with multiple fundamental modes”. In Proceedings of ASME Turbo Expo 2021 Turbomachinery Technical Conference and Exposition.